

Association of Junk Food Consumption, Skipping of Meal and Physical Activity on Menstrual Cycle of Female Undergraduate Students of Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract

Background: Menstruation is a vital indicator of women's health, and disturbances in the menstrual cycle can lead to significant long-term health consequences. Lifestyle behaviours—particularly dietary patterns and physical activity—have increasingly been recognized as modifiable determinants of menstrual irregularities. **Objective:** This study aimed to assess the prevalence of irregular menstrual cycles and explore their association with junk-food intake, meal-skipping habits, and levels of physical activity among female undergraduate students in Karachi, Pakistan. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 297 unmarried female medical students from July to October 2024. Sample size estimation was carried out using OpenEpi. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that captured demographic information, BMI, menstrual characteristics, junk-food consumption frequency, meal-skipping patterns, and physical activity levels. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 27.0 and R 4.3.3. Frequency distributions described the sample, while Chi-square or Fisher's Exact tests assessed bivariate associations. Multivariable Firth logistic regression was applied to identify independent predictors, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Regular menstrual cycles were reported by 68.5% of participants, while 31.5% experienced irregular cycles. Bivariate analysis showed significant associations between menstrual regularity and junk-food intake ($p < 0.001$), frequency of junk-food consumption ($p = 0.027$), and physical activity ($p = 0.007$). Moderate physical activity was linked to fewer irregular cycles compared with light activity. BMI, meal skipping, snacking, dieting, and sedentary behaviour were not significant predictors. In the adjusted model, junk-food consumption remained a robust independent predictor, with students reporting such diets having nearly seven times higher odds of irregular cycles (OR = 6.68; 95% CI: 2.75–17.56; $p < 0.001$). Moderate physical activity exhibited a protective effect, reducing the likelihood of irregular cycles by approximately 70% (OR = 0.32; 95% CI: 0.14–0.67; $p = 0.003$). Other variables were not statistically significant in the multivariable model.

Keywords: Female students, Menstrual cycle, Physical activity, Junk-food consumption.

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Introduction

Menstruation is a vital marker of women's overall health, and disruptions in its regularity can signal broader health concerns [1,2]. Globally, such irregularities affect 10–60% of young women [2-5].

Multiple factors contribute to menstrual irregularities [6, 7], with obesity being a key modifiable risk factor [8-10]. The higher adoption of high-fat diet, meal skipping and the transition from traditional to Western dietary habits has been escalating among young women globally [11, 12].

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Researches have been conducted to evaluate the potential connection between junk food consumption and the physical well-being of female students [9, 11, 12,13].

Consistent physical activity and a nutritious diet have proven effective in both treating and preventing menstrual disorders by playing a role in hormone regulation, mitigating the adverse impact of junk food on human body and associated abnormalities [12-16]. A study on athlete student's eating habits found that junk food consumption was very low among them as compare to non athlete [17].

Most of the researches conducted in Pakistan have primarily focused on adolescent girls [15, 18,19,20]. In this study our primary focus is to determine the prevalence of irregular cycles in adult females and to determine the association of menstrual patterns with consumption of junk food and physical activity. If the results prove to be statistically significant, they can be used to provide a basis to design targeted health interventions and allow the management of menstrual irregularities with regard to intake of junk food and exercise.

The Operational Definitions

1. Irregular menstruation: A normal menstrual cycle has a frequency of 24 to 38 days and lasts 2 to 7 days, with 5 to 80 mL of blood loss. Variations in any of these 4 parameters constitute Abnormal uterine bleeding or irregular menstruation (21).

2. Junk food: Foods high in calories, sugars, unhealthy fats and salt and low in essential nutrients vitamins, minerals and fiber are considered as junk food. These foods are processed and packaged for convenience and having little or no nutritional value (22). Junk food comprises of items such as instant noodles, biscuits, chocolates, chow mien, dumplings, soft drinks like Coke, Pepsi, Fanta, burgers, pizza, canned foods, processed meat products, fried foods like French fries, samosas, chicken nuggets, processed snacks like cheese puffs and patties, pastries and desserts such as doughnuts and cakes, sugary cereals, ice cream and microwave popcorn with added butter and salt. (23)

3. Physical activity: Physical activity is defined as any bodily movement produced by one or large muscle groups with energy expenditure 24. These activities are either moderate or vigorous in intensity. Moderate activities require some effort like brisk walking, swimming, tennis, dancing, cycling at moderate pace which is moderately increase the heart rate and breathing .Vigorous activities include aerobics, jogging and many competitive sports which makes breathe harder and significantly increase the heart rate and make conversation difficult. (25)

4. BMI Categories: For Asian adults, the WHO expert consultation defines BMI (body mass index) categories as underweight: < 18.5 kg/m², normal weight: 18.5–22.9 kg/m², overweight : 23.0–27.4 kg/m², and obesity: ≥ 27.5 kg/m².(26)

Hypothesis

There is an association between junk food consumption, skipping meal and physical activity with menstrual pattern of adult females.

Objective

- 1.To determine the prevalence of irregular cycles in adult females
- 2.To determine the association of irregular menstrual cycle with junk food consumption, skipping meal and the trend of physical activities among undergraduate female students of Karachi, Pakistan.

Methods and Materials

The current cross-sectional study was conducted at the Sir Syed College of Medical Sciences Girl's campus in Karachi, Pakistan, over a period of three months (July to October 2024). All unmarried female students between the age of 18 to 26 were included. Married females and those on hormonal pills were excluded from the study. The sample size was validated using OpenEpi software, based on a previously reported prevalence of 29% to be 297. The questionnaire was made by the primary author and though it was not a previously validated tool; however, its items were adapted from multiple published studies on similar topics to ensure content relevance. The authors reviewed and refined the questions for clarity and appropriateness, and the tool underwent a small pilot check for comprehensibility before distribution. To minimize the potential bias, the questionnaire was administered anonymously and voluntarily on their WhatsApp groups, no identifying information was collected, and the authors were not involved in tracking participation, helping ensure that students could respond freely without influence.

The questionnaire was designed with five sections designed to solicit detailed information. The first section obtained informed consent and collected demographic data from participants. The following sections examined various topics of interest such as menstrual patterns, junk food consumption, skipping meal, snacking and frequency of physical activity and sedentary hours among respondents. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 27.0 and R version 4.3.3. to get the frequency distributions for categorical variables, Bivariate associations between menstrual regularity and predictors were tested using either Chi-Square or Fisher's Exact test. These were also further examined using multivariable Firth logistic regression to identify independent predictors. p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Among the 297 participants, 50.5% were aged 19–22 years and 49.5% were 23–26 years. Based on BMI, 20.6% were underweight, 49.2% had normal weight, 28.1% were overweight, and 2% were obese. Overall, 68.5% reported regular menstrual cycles, while 31.5% experienced irregular cycles.

Table 1. Frequency distribution of different variables

Variable	Category	N	Percent
Menstrual cycle	Regular	137	68.5
	Irregular	63	31.5
Food Type	Junk food	40	20.0
Frequency of junk food	1.Never	1	0.5
	2.Rarely (less than 10% of time)	45	22.5
	3.Occasionally(about 30% of time)	86	43.0
	4.Sometimes (about 50% of time)	48	24.0
	5. Frequently (about 70% of time)	18	9.0
	6. Usually (about 90% of time)	2	1.0
Meal Skipped	Break fast	139	69.5
	Dinner	7	3.5
	Lunch	54	27.0
Frequency of snacking	1.Never	4	2.0

	2.Rarely (less than 10%)	42	21.1
	3.Occasionally(About 30%)	64	32.2
	4.Some times (About 50%)	56	28.1
	5.Frequent (About70%)	29	14.6
	6.Usually (About 90%)	3	1.5
	7.Every time	1	0.5
Dieting	1. Yes	62	31.0
	2, No	138	69.0
Exercise per Week	1.Never	11	5.5
	2.Rarely (less than 10% of time)	62	31.0
	3.Occasionally(about 30% of time)	58	29.0
	4.Sometimes (about 50% of time)	53	26.5
	5. Frequently (about 70% of time)	13	6.5
	6. Usually (about 90% of time)	2	1.0
	7. Every time	1	0.5
Physical Activity Scale	1.Light	92	46.0
	2. Moderate	87	43.5
	3. Strenuous	14	7.0
	5. i do but it varies	7	3.5
Sedentary Hours per Day	1.Less than 1 hour	5	2.5
	2.1-2 hours	47	23.5
	3.3-4 hours	41	20.5
	4.5 or more hours	106	53.0

Regarding dietary habits, 43% reported occasional fast/junk-food consumption, 24% sometimes, and 9% frequent intake. Bivariate analysis revealed a significant association between fast-food consumption and menstrual irregularity ($p < 0.001$), with the highest prevalence of irregular cycles observed among frequent consumers (p

= 0.027). Meal skipping was common, with breakfast skipped most frequently (69.5%), followed by lunch (27%) and dinner (3.5%). Snacking occurred occasionally in 32.2% and sometimes in 28.1% of participants, while 31% reported dieting.

Table 2. Bivariate analysis: Association of predictors with cycle regularity

Variable	Method	P_Value
BMI Category	Fisher's Exact Test	0.2218
Main Food Type	Fisher's Exact Test	0.0000
Fast Food Frequency	Fisher's Exact Test	0.0273
Meal Skipped	Fisher's Exact Test	0.3559
Snack Frequency	Fisher's Exact Test	0.9593
Dieting	Chi-square Test	0.7346
Exercise per Week	Fisher's Exact Test	0.0547
Physical Activity Scale	Fisher's Exact Test	0.0069
Sedentary Hours per Day	Fisher's Exact Test	0.9605

For physical activity, 31% rarely exercised, 29% occasionally, and 26.5% sometimes, with only 0.5% exercising consistently. Activity intensity was reported as light (46%), moderate (43.5%), and strenuous (7%). More than half (53%) reported sitting for over 5 hours daily.

Moderate physical activity was associated with lower odds of irregular cycles compared with light activity ($p = 0.007$). Other factors, including BMI, meal skipping, snacking, dieting, and sedentary hours, were not statistically significant.

Table 3. Multivariable regression between different variables

Predictor	OR	Lower_CI	Upper_CI	P_Value
Junk food	6.675	2.751	17.563	0.000
Fast Food Freq: Rarely	2.992	0.114	501.657	0.521
Occasionally	5.058	0.202	835.200	0.329
Sometimes	4.348	0.167	728.841	0.384
Frequently	15.455	0.558	2676.499	0.106
Usually	0.358	0.001	99.170	0.668
Physical Activity: Moderate	0.315	0.142	0.673	0.003
Strenuous	0.336	0.076	1.253	0.107
Variable	0.143	0.007	1.123	0.067
BMI: Obese	1.601	0.011	33.107	0.922
Overweight	0.457	0.181	1.085	0.076
Underweight	1.191	0.486	2.849	0.698
Age	1.034	0.831	1.288	0.763

In multivariable regression, fast-food consumption remained a strong independent predictor of irregular cycles (OR = 6.68, 95% CI: 2.75–17.56; $p < 0.001$), whereas moderate physical activity was protective, reducing the odds by approximately 70% (OR = 0.32, 95% CI: 0.14–0.67; $p = 0.003$). No significant effects were observed for BMI, dieting, sedentary behaviour, or meal skipping in the adjusted model.

Discussion

The prevalence of irregular menstruation is increasingly recognised as a significant health concern among adult females worldwide, and studies from Pakistan report a wide variation ranging between 30% and 60%. The present study is the first from Pakistan to specifically examine the association of junk-food consumption and physical activity with irregular menstruation among adult females.

In our sample, **31.5%** of women reported irregular menstrual cycles, a figure comparable to earlier findings from Ethiopia (**32.6%**) [3], Pakistan by Farhan et al. (**38%**) [5], and Chinese international students (**15.1%**) [10]. These results place our study within the mid-range of global estimates and reinforce the ongoing concern regarding menstrual irregularities among young women.

Dietary habits emerged as the strongest and most consistent predictor of irregular menstruation. Participants who consumed junk food had significantly higher odds of reporting irregular cycles. This aligns with prior research demonstrating that frequent consumption of ultra-processed, energy-dense foods is associated with reproductive disturbances. Qureshi et al. similarly reported a strong link between junk-food intake and menstrual irregularity among Pakistani university students [11]. Naz et al. found that **61%** of girls with irregular cycles consumed junk food [18], while Singh et al. also reported higher menstrual problems among fast-food consumers [13]. These findings are consistent with contemporary evidence showing that ultra-processed foods—high in sugars, unhealthy fats, and additives—exert metabolic and hormonal effects that may disrupt ovarian function [22,23].

Physical activity also showed a significant association with menstrual health. In our study, women engaging in moderate physical activity had nearly **70% lower odds** of irregular menstruation (OR = 0.32, $p = 0.003$). This supports previous literature demonstrating the regulatory effect of exercise on hormonal balance and menstrual cycle patterns. Nawaz et al. found a lower prevalence of irregular cycles among athletes than non-athletes [17], and Butt et al.'s systematic review highlighted the positive role of physical activity in improving reproductive endocrine function [14]. Evidence from international exercise guidelines similarly emphasizes that moderate-to-vigorous activity improves metabolic health and may support menstrual regularity [24,25]. These findings suggest that physical activity may offset some adverse effects of unhealthy dietary behaviours.

BMI was not a significant predictor of menstrual irregularity in the current study. However, previous research shows mixed outcomes. Agrawal et al. in India reported that overweight females were more likely to experience oligomenorrhea, while underweight individuals showed higher rates of menorrhagia [27]. Conversely, Tayebi et al. found no significant relationship between BMI and menstrual disturbances [28]. The lack of association in our study may be attributed to the limited number of obese participants, reducing the statistical power to detect BMI-related differences.

Meal skipping, dieting, snacking, and sedentary behaviour were not significantly associated with menstrual irregularity in our population. This differs from the findings of Singh et al., who reported breakfast skipping as a risk factor for irregular cycles [13]. Although breakfast was the most frequently skipped meal (69.5%) in our study, this behaviour

did not translate into measurable menstrual disruption. Similarly, the absence of significant associations with snacking and dieting contrasts with earlier studies that suggested lifestyle choices may influence menstrual health [6,12]. Cultural, behavioural, and dietary differences among Pakistani women may explain these discrepancies.

Despite these variations, it is noteworthy that the subset of women consuming fast food frequently (20%) exhibited a markedly higher risk of menstrual irregularity. This underscores a possible lifestyle transition among young Pakistani women, consistent with observations from Bangladesh [9] and Nepal [29], where increased consumption of processed food has been linked to adverse health outcomes. Fast foods are typically rich in saturated fats, refined carbohydrates, and preservatives, which may contribute to hormonal imbalance through effects on insulin resistance, inflammation, and metabolic pathways [8]. In contrast, physical activity enhances insulin sensitivity, supports hormonal regulation, and improves ovarian function, offering a potential mitigating effect [14].

Overall, the findings of this study contribute to a growing body of evidence suggesting that the combination of poor dietary habits and insufficient physical activity has meaningful implications for reproductive health. Strengthening health-promotion strategies focusing on reducing junk-food consumption and increasing physical activity could therefore play an important role in improving menstrual health among Pakistani women.

Limitations

This research offers valuable understanding of menstrual irregularities among Pakistani female university students, highlighting how poor diet may elevate risk while moderate exercise provides some protection. Nevertheless, the use of self-reported information, general dietary categories, and a sample drawn from a single institution restrict the precision and broader applicability of the results.

Conclusion and Future Recommendations:

This study contributes important evidence on how lifestyle behaviours relate to menstrual health in young Pakistani women, supporting the development of educational initiatives and interventions that encourage healthier habits and aim to reduce menstrual disturbances. Future research should incorporate more detailed assessments of physical activity and employ longitudinal methods to better establish causal relationships.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization: Bushra Zulfiqar (BZ), Amber Mushtaq (AM), Fatima Rafique. **Study Design:** Amber Mushtaq (AM), Shweta Darshan (SD), Sapna Kishnoomal (SK) **Methodology, Data Analysis and Interpretation:** Fatima Rafique (FR), Sapna Kishnoomal (SK), Monika Kumari (MK). **Writing – Draft, Critical Review, and Revision:** Amber Mushtaq, Shweta Darshan (SD), Bushra Zulfiqar (BZ). **Final Approval & Proof for Publication:** All authors.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request

Ethical Approval

The study has been approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Sir Syed College of Medical Sciences Trust and assigned the reference number 028 SSCMS- Ethics/2023.

Consent to Participate

Informed consent has been obtained from the study participants.

Consent for Publication

All authors have proof read the article and approved for publication.

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